

Diversity of Medium and Large-sized mammals of district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Pakistan is distinguished by a diverse range of mammalian species. The primary goals of this research are to learn about the diversity mammals in Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. During the surveys, total 9 species were collected through direct count method, the Shannon-Weiner diversity index was 0.74. Dominant species is Asiatic Jackal with relative abundance is 0.48387, while other species i.e. Himalayan Palm Civet (RA=0.12903), small Kashmir flying squirrel (RA=0.09677), Indian crested porcupine (RA=0.06452), Indian wild boar (RA=0.06452), small Indian civet (RA=0.06452), common leopard (RA=0.03226), Indian fox (RA=0.03226) and small Indian mongoose (RA=0.03226) are also documented in Bagh (Figure 2).

Keywords: Mammals, Bagh, Diversity, Species, Mountain

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INTRODUCTION

Mammalian species are among the most abundant resources on the planet. Mammals provide a range of functions in terrestrial ecosystems, including ecological indicator, cultural, educational, economic, and scientific aspects. Large and medium-sized animals are critical to ecosystem function. Large and medium-sized animals play vital roles in forest ecosystems by managing prey populations and disseminating seeds. Despite the fact that big and medium-sized animals provide different tasks, they are both endangered by human-caused causes (Bogoni *et al.*, 2017; Qufa and Bekele, 2019; Babar and Kanwal, 2021).

Terrestrial animals are helpful in identifying conservation priority regions. Metrics such as the number of species now occupying a certain region, historical distribution evidence, and the level of threat to the species all help with conservation work (Myers, 1990; Myers *et al.*, 2000). More than “4763 mammalian species and 195 species are identified till now in the world and Pakistan respectively (IUCN, 2002; Roberts, 2005; Watson and Roberts, 2015; Altaf, 2016). Pakistan has portions of three bio-geographic areas, namely the Palearctic, Oriental, and Ethiopian, and as a result exhibits diverse forms of variety

Out of Total “12 mammalian species are Critically Endangered”, “12 mammalian species are Endangered”, “20 Vulnerable”, “32 Near Threatened” , “71

Least Concern”, “38 Data Deficient” and “8 are Regionally Extinct” in this country (IUCN, 2003). Temperature rises disturb hibernation, diminish water availability in desert regions, produce extreme weather events, and transmit infections, all of which affect mammalian diversity. A reduction in precipitation has been connected to the demise of numerous big animal species in Africa. Precipitation reduces plant growth and raises the risk of predation (Ogutu and Owen-Smith, 2003; Musiega and Kazadi, 2004; Garcia-Solache and Casadevall, 2010). This research is intended to identify the mammalian diversity of Bagh district, AJ&K, Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mammalian species were collected from October 2016 to September 2020.

STUDY AREA

Bagh is located in mountainous state, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The variations in elevation cause of different temperature, humidity, rainfall, and snowfall (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of study area (Riaz and Altaf, 2021).

ASSESSMENT OF MAMMALIAN DIVERSITY

The “linear count method” was utilized to know diversity, data were collected direct count method i.e. voices as well as number count.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The diversity of Bagh district was calculated through “Shannon-wiener diversity index” i.e. H' (Shannon and Weaver, 1949) using following formula;

$$“H' = - [\sum PI \ln PI]”$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In district Bagh, total 9 species of mammals are documented. In table 1, Shannon-wiener Diversity Index for mammalian species in study area was as 0.740. Dominant species was Asiatic Jackal with relative abundance is 0.48387, while other species i.e. Himalayan Palm Civet (RA=0.12903), small Kashmir flying squirrel (RA=0.09677), Indian crested porcupine (RA=0.06452), Indian wild boar (RA=0.06452), small Indian civet (RA=0.06452), common leopard (RA=0.03226), Indian fox (RA=0.03226) and small Indian mongoose (RA=0.03226) are also extant in Bagh (Figure 2). Altaf *et al.* (2014) documented “15 mammalian species” from head Marala, Khanki and Qadirabad. Mammalian species are also identified and documented from other parts of Pakistan (Altaf, 2018; Haider and Altaf, 2018; Kanwal *et al.*, 2019; Afsheen *et al.*, 2020; Aslam and Faiz, 2020; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Rasheed *et al.*, 2020; Abbasi, 2021; Haidar, 2021; Ijaz and Adil, 2021; Riaz and Altaf, 2021).

Figure 2: Diversity of Mammalian Species of the Bagh.

Table 1: the diversity of Mammals in the study area.

Sr.	Names	Pi/RA	LogPi	PilogPi
	Asiatic Jackal			
1	<i>Canis aureus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	0.484	-0.315	-0.153
	Common Leopard			
2	<i>Panthera pardus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	0.032	-1.491	-0.048
	Himalayan Palm Civet			
3	<i>Paguma larvata</i> Smith, 1827	0.129	-0.889	-0.115
	Indian Crested Porcupine			
4	<i>Hystrix indica</i> Kerr, 1792	0.065	-1.190	-0.077
5	Indian Fox	0.032	-1.491	-0.048

	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i> Linnaeus, 1758			
	Indian Wild Boar			
6	<i>Sus scrofa</i> Linnaeus, 1758	0.065	-1.190	-0.077
	Small Indian Civet			
7	<i>Viverricula indica</i> Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1803	0.065	-1.190	-0.077
	Small Indian Mongoose			
8	<i>Herpestes javanicus</i> É. Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1818	0.032	-1.491	-0.048
	Small Kashmir Flying Squirrel			
9	<i>Holopetes fimbriatus</i> Fischer, 1853	0.097	-1.014	-0.098
Total		1.000		-0.740
	Shannon-wiener diversity index i.e. H'			0.740

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